

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES AND PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE OF OAT PLANTS AND OAT MEAL

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Abstract: Nowadays, it is of great importance to maintain the health of the population and provide it with quality food products. Accordingly, the oat (*Avena sativa* L.) plant and oat milk obtained from it are rich in biologically active substances, in particular, beta-glucans, proteins, vitamins (group B, vitamin E) and mineral elements. In this article, we paid great attention to the important medicinal value of oat products in improving the functioning of the cardiovascular system, reducing blood cholesterol levels, normalizing the digestive process and strengthening the immune system. Oat milk is lactose-free and cholesterol-free, and is a useful alternative for people with allergies to dairy products and those who adhere to a diet. At the same time, we studied measures to implement the widespread use of oat milk in the food industry in the production of functional products, medicine and dietetics. In our scientific research results, we have presented the importance of oats and products based on them in a healthy diet, based on the prospects for their practical implementation.

Keywords: Oats, oat groats, lactose, cholesterol, diabetes mellitus, phenolic compounds, chemical composition, agrobiological requirements, endosperm, fiber, polysaccharides, antioxidant.

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda aholi salomatligini saqlash, sifatli oziq – ovqat mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Bunga asosan, suli (*Avena sativa* L.) o'simligi va undan olinadigan suli yormasi suti biologik faol moddalar, xususan, beta-glyukanlar, oqsillar, vitaminlar (B guruhi, E vitamini) hamda mineral elementlarga boyligi bilan ajralib turadi. Ushbu maqolamizda suli

mahsulotini yurak-qon tomir tizimi faoliyatini yaxshilash, qonda xolesterin miqdorini kamaytirish, ovqat hazm qilish jarayonini me'yorlashtirish va immun tizimini mustahkamlashda muhim shifobaxsh ahamiyatga egaligiga katta e'tibor qaratdik. Suli yormasi suti laktozasiz va xolesterinsiz bo'lib, sut mahsulotlariga allergiyasi bo'lgan shaxslar hamda parhez bop ovqatlanishga rioya qiluvchilar uchun foydali muqobil hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, suli yormasi suti oziq-ovqat sanoatida funksional mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishda, tibbiyot va parhezshunoslikda keng qo'llanishini amaliyotga tadbiq etish choralarini o'rganib chiqdik. Ilmiy tadqiqot natijalarimizda suli va uning asosidagi mahsulotlarning sog'lom ovqatlanish tizimidagi ahamiyatini, ularni amaliyotga joriy etish istiqbollari asosida olib berdik.

Аннотация: В настоящее время поддержание здоровья населения и обеспечение его качественными продуктами питания имеет огромное значение. Соответственно, овес (*Avena sativa* L.) и получаемое из него овсяное молоко богаты биологически активными веществами, в частности, бета-глюканами, белками, витаминами (группа В, витамин Е) и минеральными элементами. В данной статье мы уделили большое внимание важной лечебной ценности овсяных продуктов в улучшении функционирования сердечно-сосудистой системы, снижении уровня холестерина в крови, нормализации пищеварения и укреплении иммунной системы. Овсяное молоко не содержит лактозы и холестерина и является полезной альтернативой для людей с аллергией на молочные продукты и для тех, кто придерживается диеты. Одновременно мы изучили меры по внедрению широкого использования овсяного молока в пищевой промышленности при производстве функциональных продуктов, лекарственных средств и диетических продуктов. В результатах наших научных исследований мы представили важность овса и продуктов на его основе в здоровом питании, основываясь на перспективах их практического

применения.

Kalit so‘zlar: Suli, suli yormasi, laktoza, xolestrin, qandli diabet, fenol birikmalar, kimyoviy tarkibi, agrobiologik talablar, endosperm, klechatka, polisaxaridlar, antioksidant.

Ключевые слова: овес, овсяная крупа, лактоза, холестерин, сахарный диабет, фенольные соединения, химический состав, агробиологические требования, эндосперм, клетчатка, полисахариды, антиоксидант.

Nowadays, maintaining the health of the population and providing it with high-quality food products is of great importance. Plant science is one of the main branches of agriculture. Its main object is green plants, which in nature have the ability to create organic substances from inorganic elements. By planting and growing green plants, a person converts the kinetic energy of sunlight into the potential energy of organic substances contained in plants. In agriculture, green plants become the main means of production in agriculture. People receive the necessary basic food products, as well as raw materials for food, light industry and other industries from agriculture. Determining the chemical composition of plant species growing in different climatic conditions in the world and processing them to obtain food products necessary for human needs is one of the urgent problems. In this regard, based on new varieties of nutritious plants, biologically active compounds that replace synthetic drugs and contain methods for treating and preventing various diseases in the human body, It is important to develop natural, harmless, environmentally friendly food supplements that contain macro and microelements and use them in folk medicine. Today, new biologically active food supplements based on plants are produced in the following assortment: tablets, capsules, powder, oil, mixture, tincture, oil and other forms. Winter cereals (winter wheat, winter barley, winter rye) are sown in the fall and harvested in the summer of the following year. Development of a technology for the production of condensed milk products based on oat milk using natural sweeteners is a scientific

innovation in the field of innovative food technology.

Oats (*Avena sativa* L.) are one of the most important cereals in the world, characterized by their high biologically active substances and wide range of uses. Oat groats are highly valued as an important raw material in human nutrition, in the production of dietary foods, as well as in the animal husbandry, pharmaceutical and cosmetology industries. The presence of beta-glucans, avenanthramides, unsaturated fatty acids, and easily digestible proteins in their composition makes them a product with biological value that distinguishes them from other cereals. The botanical properties, chemical composition, agrobiological requirements, and practical importance of oats are described in detail below. Based on this, we focused on the morphological, physiological, ecological, and biological characteristics of the oat plant. Oats are an annual herbaceous plant belonging to the Poaceae (cereal) family, which differs in a number of ways from other cereals - wheat, barley, and rye. The structure of the oat stem, the type of flowering, the anatomical features of the seeds, and the structure of the panicle-shaped flowers characterize it as a unique plant. Oats have a fibrous root system, which develops from the lower joints of the stem. Its roots penetrate the soil to a depth of 70-100 cm. Due to the well-developed roots, the plant absorbs moisture well, but is less drought-resistant than wheat. The roots effectively absorb minerals such as phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, and microelements from the soil. The stem of oats is cylindrical, hollow, and consists of joints. The height of the stem varies from 50 to 150 cm, depending on agrotechnical, variety, and climatic conditions. The diameter of the stem is 3-6 mm, and it is softer and more flexible than the stem of wheat. The structure of the oat leaf is linear, 1-3 cm wide, and 20-35 cm long. The leaf sheaths partially surround the stem, and the leaf plate is slightly wider than the stem. The leaf surface is moderately hairy, which increases its adaptability to cold and wet conditions. Oats have a complex panicle-type inflorescence. The head does not have spikelets like cereals. Each branch has 2-3 flowers, which are surrounded by bracts (lemma and

palea). The inflorescence is anemophilous, i.e. pollinated by the wind. The anatomical structure of the grain - the oat grain can be glassy or spongy. The grain consists of the following layers: The husk (25-30%) - the fibrous part, rich in silica and lignin. The grain is mainly separated during processing. The endosperm (60-65%) - contains the main part of starch, proteins and polysaccharides. The embryo (2-3%) - is rich in fats, enzymes, vitamin E and other biologically active substances. Since the oat grain husk is hard, special technological processes are used to obtain the groats.

Oatmeal has a high biological and nutritional value. Its composition is much richer and more diverse than other cereals. Starch is the main source of energy in the grain. It contains amylose and amylopectin in an optimal ratio.

Fiber - 10-12%. Oats contain more fiber than other cereals, which increases its value as a dietary product. Beta-glucan - 3-6%. One of the most important biological components of oatmeal, it has the property of improving the functioning of the cardiovascular system, reducing cholesterol levels. Vitamin and mineral composition - Oatmeal is very rich in the following substances as a source of biologically active substances:

Vitamins: B1, B2, B3, B6, E, K, foliy acid.

Minerals: Fe, Zn, Mg, Ca, P, K, Mn.

Antioxidants: avenanthramides are unique phenolic compounds with anti-inflammatory properties. This rich composition of oats gives grounds to consider it "the most nutritious grain". Growth environment and agrobiological requirements of the oat plant: Oats grow well in temperate and cold climate zones. They are moisture-loving, frost-resistant, but their yield decreases in dry, hot climates. Climate requirements: Germination temperature: 3-5°C, optimal vegetation temperature: 15-20°C, frost resistance: withstands up to -3°C during the initial development period. Oats do not develop well in hot climates, especially at temperatures above 30°C, growth slows down. Soil requirements: Oats are

considered undemanding cereals, but: they grow well on light and medium loamy soils. The optimal indicator for soil pH is 6.0-7.5. Moderately resistant to salinity. Sufficient organic matter in the soil is important for the complete nutrition of the plant. Moisture requirements: Oats require good moisture. Around 400-500 mm of precipitation or irrigation is required during the vegetation period. Agrotechnical requirements: Sown in early spring, as it tolerates frost well. Average ripening period is 80-110 days. Yield is 2.5-4.0 t/ha, with high agrotechnical conditions it can be more than 5 t/ha.

The practical importance of oatmeal - oats are used in many areas. For example: from the food industry to animal husbandry, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and the production of biologically active additives. In the food industry - oatmeal is widely used in the production of the following products: Oat porridge, Oat flour, Muesli and granola, Oat cookies, Diet breads, Oat milk (plant-based milk). Oat milk has long occupied an important place among vegetarians and lactose-intolerant people. When natural sweeteners are added to oat milk, its taste and attractiveness for consumers increase. In medicine and dietetics - it lowers blood cholesterol (beta-glucan effect), stabilizes blood sugar, improves intestinal function, is less allergenic, low in saturated fats, effective in preventing cardiovascular diseases, especially avenanthramides are very important as a natural antioxidant that reduces inflammatory processes in the body. In animal husbandry - Oats are a fodder product with high nutritional value, and are considered a good feed for horses, cattle and poultry. Oat straw is also valued as an easily digestible feed. Industrial use - Oat oil is used in the cosmetology industry to prepare skin softening creams and face masks. Beta-glucan is used in the pharmaceutical industry to produce biologically active additives. Various polysaccharides and dietary fibers are extracted from oat grains. Oatmeal is a cereal product with high biological, nutritional and dietary value. Its plant is frost-resistant, not demanding on soil and moisture, and in terms of chemical composition it has more biologically active

substances than other cereals. The presence of beta-glucan, avenanthramide, polyene fatty acids and high-quality proteins makes oats an important component of a modern healthy nutrition system. Also, its wide use in the food, livestock, pharmaceutical and cosmetology industries, as well as its appreciation as an environmentally friendly and easily digestible product, makes oats one of the most promising cereals today.

Chemical composition of oat grain:

№	Nutrients	Amount (100%)
1	Protein	12-17%
2	Lipids	5-8%
3	Carbohydrate	In dry oat grain, 65-67% In oatmeal, 60-66%
4	Strach	55-60%

The literature review shows that the oat plant (*Avena sativa* L.) and oat groats obtained from it are of high scientific and practical importance as functional food raw materials rich in biologically active substances. Oat grains are characterized by the presence of high molecular weight polysaccharides, nutrients, proteins, fats, starch and carbohydrates. This complex of components determines the physiological and therapeutic effectiveness of oat products.

Based on the above, we conducted our scientific research in the dehkan farms of the Fergana region and in the scientific research laboratory of the Department of OOT and X "of the Fergana State Technical University. In this, we determined the amount of dry matter in the oat plant using a refractometer device. In this case, 200 g of oat groats were boiled in 600 g of water, removed from the blender, and the resulting milk was dropped into the refractometer device by dropping 2-3 drops and checked. The results of laboratory processes using the refractometer device: Oat goat milk was determined at a concentration of 1 in the refractometer device at

room temperature of -20 C, and the amount of dry matter in 100 g was determined. Sucrose - 4%, lactose - 1%, mineral matter -0.5%, protein -0.5%. In order to obtain milk (a plant-based drink) from oat groats, the main method of extraction (hydroextraction) is wet extraction. and colloidal dispersion methods are used. This process is called "aqueous extraction method" or "technology for obtaining milk analogues from plant raw materials" in food technology. Because the physicochemical and colloidal properties of oat milk are significantly different from animal milk. Therefore, aspects such as heat and mass transfer during their condensation, rheological changes, viscosity dynamics, and thermostable behavior of sweeteners were studied in the course of our scientific research.

At the same time, the morphological, anatomical, physiological and biological characteristics of the oat plant were studied according to the literature review.

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